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ME

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DAM4CO₂

Double-Active Membranes for a sustainable CO₂ cycle

About us

DAM4CO₂, responding to the call "EIC Pathfinder Challenge: Carbon dioxide and nitrogen management and valorisation", aims at changing the existing paradigm within separation and utilization of CO₂ by coupling membrane and catalytic technologies.

DAM4CO₂ develops a novel membrane technology for the simultaneous CO₂ separation and its photocatalytic conversion to C₁-C₉ molecules, as renewable fuels. The project will deliver a prototype, designed using the design-build-test-learn approach, for a proof-of-concept validation that will be tested in lab-conditions. The DBTL approach is inherent in each scientific/technological WP of the project.

Close attention will be paid to the use of non-critical raw materials at any stage of the process, and the carbon-neutrality in order to reverse the increase of greenhouse gases emissions to mitigate the serious consequences on the global climate and to achieve the goals of the European Green Deal.

Its waste to- valuable concept will contribute to lower the impact of human activities on the environment and building a more just society.

Objective

- Use of non-critical raw materials at any stage of the project
- Greener material and protocols for membrane production

- Development of the next generation membranes for CO₂ capture using advanced polymers and MOFs
- Development of photocatalytic membranes using mono and bi-functional catalysts for CO₂ conversion into C₁-C₉ molecules

- Integration of the CO₂ management and valorisation processes into a single device
- Design of novel membrane modules

Impact

DAM4CO₂ will make real the concept of "waste-to-valuable" for CO₂ emission.

Drastic reduction of plant size, construction costs and energy requirements for CO₂ capture and conversion processes.

The development of viable CCU processes will also enable emissions-intense industries to become environmentally sustainable without losing profitability and jobs.

Who we are

UPV-ITQ (ES)

USWAN (UK)

ME-SEP (PL)

PRIMALCHIT (ES)